

Inclusive Citizenship in a world in Transformation: Co-Designing for Democracy

Citizens
Reinventing
Democracy

Inclusive Citizenship in a world in Transformation: Co-Designing for Democracy

3.1 Dialogue Tool based on the HUMAT Framework and Instructions for Users

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Executive Summary

The INCITE-DEM project, funded by the EU's Horizon Europe initiative, spans three years from March 2023 to February 2026, aimed at enhancing inclusive citizen participation. Through a collaborative approach involving ten partners in nine countries, the project endeavours to address contemporary societal challenges while co-creating innovative democratic mechanisms. Development of the dialogue tool based on HUMAT is one of the most important missions in INCITE-DEM.

This deliverable revolves around the design and development of an innovative dialogue tool, aimed at augmenting user engagement and fostering effective decision-making within community contexts.

The design and integration phase focuses on crafting a robust foundation for the dialogue tool. This involves planning and execution to ensure functionality and user-friendly interactions. Our objective is to enhance the tool's adaptability to diverse community settings, facilitating a wide range of meaningful conversations.

The user interface development aspect is dedicated to creating an intuitive and visually appealing interface. The emphasis is on providing users with an effortless and enjoyable experience, promoting increased participation and involvement. Through thoughtful design choices, we aim to simplify complex decision-making processes within the community framework. A pivotal component of our endeavour is the production of an engaging introductory video. This video serves as a key resource, acquainting viewers with the simulation and elucidating fundamental concepts of decision-making in a community context.

Early exploration with the dialogue tool is integral to our approach. We recognise the importance of user feedback and iterative refinement. Our team is committed to actively involving users in the initial phases, ensuring that the tool aligns with the dynamic needs of communities. This collaborative approach enhances the tool's effectiveness and relevance in real-world scenarios.

In conclusion, our comprehensive strategy for the design and development of the dialogue tool encompasses not only the technical aspects but also the user experience and educational components. By focusing on adaptability, user-friendliness, and educational outreach, we aim to create a tool that empowers communities to make informed decisions through meaningful dialogue.

1 Introduction

The challenge of adapting to dynamic environmental and climatic conditions is an increasingly pressing issue for communities worldwide (Piggott-McKellar et al., 2019; McNamara & Buggy, 2017). As various initiatives strive to address these challenges, active community participation becomes a necessity (Samaddar et al., 2019 & 2021). The collaborative engagement and concerted efforts of a community are crucial for the successful implementation of measures such as isolating residences, establishing heat networks, and fostering communal vehicular sharing. This participatory dimension aligns with the foundational principles of democracy, prompting fundamental questions about the collective decision-making process in the face of diverse perspectives and interests.

However, local policy implementation encounters obstacles, particularly in the realm of sustainable energy practices, where community members may resist proposed plans due to a lack of awareness and ineffective communication (Sovacool, 2018; Dobravec et al., 2021). Balancing citizen input with authoritative action is essential for a smooth transition, but disputes among citizens can impede meaningful dialogue, hindering progress despite the urgent need for change (Boehnke et al., 2023; Michels & De Graaf, 2010). To address these challenges, democratic innovations (DIs)—tailored institutions designed to amplify citizen participation—have gained prominence (Smith, 2009). These innovations, such as participatory budgeting, referendums, mini-publics, digital participation, and more, strive to address democratic deficiencies ranging from public distrust in political institutions to inefficiencies in policy outcomes (Elstub & Escobar, 2019).

The adoption of DIs often involves citizen participation in the planning process through field experiments (Voinov et al., 2016 & 2018). However, frictions and challenges impact citizens' willingness to engage, affecting their satisfaction with operational aspects and shaping the overall effectiveness of participatory initiatives (Van Bruggen et al., 2019). In this context, computer simulation emerges as a powerful tool within participatory modelling (PM), providing a virtual realm for understanding complex systems without immediate real-world consequences (Le Page et al., 2012; Basco-Carrera et al., 2017).

Agent-based modelling (ABM) stands out as a widely recognised simulation technique extensively employed in socio-ecological systems for comprehensively capturing the dynamic behaviour and evolving states of the system over time (Schulze et al., 2017; Hansen & Morrison, 2019). In the EU SMARTEES¹ project, Antosz et al (2019) developed the ABM framework HUMAT to delve into social innovation dynamics. HUMAT formalises diverse behavioural drivers, aiding model development and data collection for parameterisation. While simulation modelling offers insights into policy effects before implementation, ethical concerns arise regarding potential manipulative use and the impact on local democracy (Anzola et al., 2022; Shults & Wildman, 2020).

One of the focal investigations within the EU INCITE-DEM² project aims to examine the feasibility and effectiveness of incorporating simulations into the planning process, specifically concentrating on improving community dialogues. The inquiry initiates a comprehensive review of agent-based modelling in participatory modelling for democratic innovations, highlighting the potential benefits of developing a dialogue tool based on HUMAT. This tool aims to simulate the dynamics of behaviours and opinions during decision-making processes, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of democratic engagement.

¹ SMARTEES homepage <https://local-social-innovation.eu/>.

² INCITE-DEM homepage <https://incite-dem.eu/>.

In Section 2, we explore the methodology of agent-based modelling for democratic innovations. We introduce the pivotal role of ABM in participatory modelling for democratic innovations, define what constitutes an agent-based model, and clarify key concepts within ABM. Furthermore, we present the research architecture of HUMAT.

Moving to Section 3, we introduce a dialogue tool crafted to cultivate mutual understanding among varied stakeholders, ultimately fostering meaningful discussions that enhance the inclusivity of democratic innovations. The section begins by stating the tool's purpose and introducing fundamental concepts related to its functionality. Following this, we delve into the tool's development, providing instructions for access and guidance on its utilisation.

In Section 4, we showcase the practical application of the dialogue tool. This includes detailing the setup of experiments, presenting observations, and highlighting the characteristics of the tool.

Finally, Section 5 conducts demonstration experiments through the dialogue tool, creating various scenarios tailored to participants' contexts, such as scenarios with happy supporters, a divided community, and unhappy supporters. The objective is to familiarise participants with the tool and encourage them to explore personalised scenarios based on their specific contexts, ultimately facilitating meaningful discussions through the tool.

2 Methodology

2.1 ABM enhancing participation in democratic innovation

In the pursuit of democratic innovation (DI), a collective effort is underway to tackle the diverse challenges facing democracy, including issues such as public distrust, lack of citizen participation in decision-making processes and inefficiencies in policy implementation (Smith, 2009). A crucial element of this endeavour is the proactive involvement of citizens in the decision-making process. Participatory modelling (PM) has become a vital strategy for achieving this objective, offering a dynamic platform that motivates stakeholders to share their local knowledge, preferences, and insights at every stage of the modelling process. Various tools and methods, as outlined by Voinov et al. (2016), underpin and enhance this participatory engagement.

The interdependent connection between PM and DI is clear (Giannelos, 2023). PM functions as a platform where stakeholders can actively engage in decision-making, emphasising collaborative learning to enhance system understanding among participants (Duea et al., 2022; Robinson & Fuller, 2017). The involvement of stakeholders in model development guarantees an accurate representation of social dynamics, aligning the models with the community's needs and interests, as highlighted by Stave (2010).

Within the diverse array of tools and methodologies in participatory modelling, one method stands out—Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) (Abar et al., 2017). ABM serves as a simulation technique that explores the behaviour of a system and how its state changes over time (Macal & North, 2010; Antelmi et al., 2022). In contrast to conventional approaches, ABM adopts a bottom-up approach, focusing on individual elements and their interactions to clarify macro-patterns and interactions within heterogeneous conditions. ABMs excel in modelling decentralised, autonomous decision-making scenarios, as demonstrated by Tesfatsion (2023).

The integration of ABM into the framework of promoting inclusive and participatory democracy pioneers a validated methodology (Dobracev et al., 2021; Bousquet et al., 2002). By incorporating ABM into the dialogical process, citizens actively engage in decision-making, fostering interactive discussions that transcend diverse backgrounds and perspectives. ABM plays a pivotal role in democratic innovation by facilitating scenario exploration. Through this, participants can visualise complex systems, enhancing their comprehension of intricate dynamics. This visualisation not only aids in communication but also contributes to cultivating a shared understanding among participants, promoting cohesion in democratic deliberations (Nugroho & Uehara, 2023). Moreover, the iterative nature of ABM, when employed as a part of a secure environment, supports research on continuous growth and evolution (Liang et al, 2022). This feature allows participants to collectively advance their understanding through ongoing dialogue and contribute to shaping policies and solutions.

In utilising ABM as a dialogue tool to investigate community dynamics, our objective is to foster positive discussions within local democratic processes. The key aim is to promote well-informed and inclusive decision-making. Through the development of a model that simulates individual opinions and behaviours within a community setting, we establish ABM as a powerful tool to enhance transparency and collaboration in local democracy.

2.2 ABM to simulate societies as systems

In our increasingly interconnected world, understanding complex systems has become indispensable, with ecosystems, the human brain, and social networks serving as prime examples (Szell et al., 2010). These systems, characterised by interconnected components and nonlinear dynamics (Levin et al., 2013), give rise to emergent properties that challenge traditional research methods and

mathematical modelling, particularly when experimenting directly with practical scenarios that might lead to irreversible changes or adverse effects.

In this complex landscape, Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) emerges as a powerful tool for comprehending complex systems (Polhill et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021). By replicating fundamental scenarios and micro-level behaviours, ABM scrutinises the occurrence processes and mutual influences of diverse phenomena, shedding light on the laws governing the evolution of complex systems (An et al., 2021).

To grasp the essence of ABM, it is crucial to define an "agent." According to Minsky (1988), in societal contexts, agents are entities engaged in collaborative problem-solving through negotiation. Governed by simple rules, these agents exhibit behaviours and interact with counterparts, influencing each other's actions. Individualised modelling of agents allows for a comprehensive examination of diversity, leading to emergent system-wide behaviour. In ABM, an agent can represent an individual, organisation, robot, or vehicle, characterised by autonomy, reactivity, initiative, and social ability (Minsky, 1988).

ABM shifts the experimental process to an "artificial society" within a computational environment. Leveraging the simplicity of artificial societies, ABM focuses on dynamic interactions, revealing the complexity and evolution rules of real systems. Its strength lies in constructing relevant artificial societies, enabling the simulation of complex systems challenging to replicate in traditional laboratories. ABM's ability to model each agent individually offers a promising method for investigating social dynamics, allowing the exploration of emerging behaviours and the simultaneous control of multiple influencing factors (Van Rooy et al., 2016).

In essence, ABM is a methodological approach employed for simulating intricate systems through the representation of discrete entities, termed agents, and their dynamic interactions within a specified environment. ABMs encompass several fundamental elements (Wilensky & Rand, 2015):

- (1) *Agents*: These discrete entities constitute the simulation, representing individuals, groups, or any entities endowed with decision-making capabilities. Agents engage in interactions with both other agents and the encompassing environment.
- (2) *Environment*: This refers to the space or context in which the agents operate and interact. It defines the boundaries and constraints within which agents can move, communicate, and influence one another, manifesting as physical, social, or abstract dimensions.
- (3) *Interactions*: Governed by explicit rules, interactions dictate how agents engage with one another and with the environment. These rules encompass diverse facets such as communication, cooperation, competition, and other forms of social or economic exchange. Interactions can exhibit varying levels of complexity and may involve parameters like proximity, social status, or resource availability. These interactions drive the dynamics of the system, leading to emergent properties and patterns.
- (4) *Emergence*: A pivotal aspect of ABMs, emergence denotes the phenomenon where complex patterns and behaviours manifest at a macroscopic level due to the interactions among individual agents. These emergent properties often cannot be predicted solely by examining the behaviour of individual agents. This emergence provides insight into the behaviour of complex systems that might be challenging to study through traditional methodologies.
- (5) *Evolution*: ABMs often incorporate the concept of evolution, enabling agents to evolve their traits and attributes over time, including behaviour patterns and decision-making strategies. Through interactions with the environment and other agents, they dynamically adapt and evolve, responding to shifting environmental conditions. This process fosters the evolution of complex behaviours and system dynamics within ABMs.

2.3 HUMAT as a framework for use with ABM

HUMAT serves as a foundational architecture for constructing artificial populations, specifically focusing on the intricacies of agent cognitions, decision-making, and social interactions rooted in social scientific theory (Antosz et al, 2019). In the realm of real-world social dynamics, encompassing phenomena like social innovations (SI), opinion dynamics, and behavioural transitions (Nyborg et al., 2016), a multitude of individuals connected in social networks make decisions based on their interests, share information, and are influenced by societal norms. These individuals navigate challenging choices, often balancing short-term gratification, social impacts, and personal values. This navigation leads to interactions that result in the diffusion of new behaviours, the formation of opposing opinion groups, and the emergence of tipping points that favour particular norms.

The HUMAT architecture systematically formalises the various drivers and processes that underlie complex social dynamics. The initiation of agent activity unfolds through multiple stages, as depicted in Figure 1 (refer to Antosz et al, 2019 for a detailed description). This initiation is grounded in the satisfaction (or dissatisfaction) of various behavioural alternatives, categorised into three distinct groups of needs within HUMAT: experiential needs, social needs (Deci & Ryan, 2000), and values. This categorisation introduces the potential for trade-offs among different need groups, impacting the cognitive dissonances (Li et al., 2020) experienced by agents and influencing their information processing and chosen actions.

After evaluating the satisfaction levels of the available behavioural alternatives, HUMAT chooses the most satisfying option. When at least two alternatives offer similar satisfaction, HUMAT delves deeper into these options, taking into account the cognitive dissonance each may provoke. Then, the option requiring the least effort to alleviate dissonance would be chosen.

Figure 1: Implementing actions within the HUMAT architecture

When an action is carried out and cognitive dissonance persists, HUMAT persists in probing the ego-network or ego-centric networks (Arnaboldi et al., 2016). These networks specifically map the connections of and from the perspective of an individual, seeking additional information that may alleviate dissonance or offer better behavioural alternatives.

HUMATs possess cognitive representations of past evaluations of potential behavioural alternatives, resulting in a dynamic individual ranking of these options. The ordering of the memory stack evolves based on experienced satisfaction, varying weights assigned to outcomes, the addition of new outcomes, and the current focal need. These dynamic processes shape the composition and order of the behavioural stack, offering a comprehensive insight into how HUMAT captures and processes information in response to the intricate dynamics of decision-making.

2.4 Summary

This section is dedicated to introducing the Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) approach and interpreting its potential impact on democratic innovation (DI). As we delve into the methodology, this section underscores the value of ABM in enriching participation in democratic processes. It highlights the dynamic nature of ABM and its proficiency in simulating complex systems, particularly in fostering inclusive and participatory democracy.

Moreover, this section introduces a comprehensive research framework - HUMAT, designed to function as a foundational architecture for constructing artificial populations, specifically focusing on the intricacies of agent cognitions, decision-making, and social interactions rooted in social scientific theory.

In the upcoming section, we will strategically integrate this framework into the democratic landscape, serving as the foundation for the development of a dialogue tool. The objective of this tool is to implement a well-structured and highly effective approach, actively fostering citizen engagement and facilitating informed decision-making.

3 A dialogue tool for INCITE-DEM

3.1 Towards a dialogue tool

3.1.1 Purpose of the dialogue tool

In scientific research employing simulation methods, the aim is typically to precisely model real-world phenomena. However, in the realm of developing a dialogue tool, faithfully replicating reality might not be the most effective strategy. Instead, our goal is to integrate this tool into participatory processes within DLabs (Democracy Labs), supported by contextual frameworks and supplemented by activities like vision workshops and provotyping (Boer & Donovan, 2012). This approach allows us to present simulation outcomes that stimulate constructive discussions, fostering a community-oriented mindset. Acknowledging the significance of diverse viewpoints, our tool strives to highlight shared perspectives and amplify conflicting interests without worsening conflicts. By illustrating the potential consequences of discord, it encourages consensus-building to avoid undesirable outcomes in the planning process.

To address societal concerns regarding polarisation and its impact on democratic processes, our exploration involves magnifying conflicting dynamics and reinforcing social elements within our dialogue tool. While the simulated social dynamics may be exaggerated, they remain recognisable by touching upon local community features. Individuals, upon recognising themselves and others in the simulation, may find amusement, steering the discussion toward a more connecting level. Drawing from the literature, we acknowledge the potential role of humour and laughter as essential elements in negotiations (Maemura & Horita, 2012).

This dialogue tool is specifically crafted to simulate the dynamics governing the evolution of opinions and behaviours on a plan among individuals (referred to as agents) within a community over time. Its primary goal is to investigate the evolution of opinions and behaviours and, secondarily, to promote dialogues among community members about the simulation outcomes, thereby fostering civic inclusivity and enhancing engagement.

Within this context, individuals are classified to foster inclusion, particularly of minority or disadvantaged groups. Our inspiration stems from the Sinus Milieus³ (Groh-Samberg et al., 2023; Schwarz & Ernst, 2009), which organises individuals with similar values, lifestyles, and social situations into groups of "like-minded" individuals, representing various value-based segments within society. These segments traditionally encompass social status (upper, middle, lower class) and fundamental values (tradition, modernisation, reorientation). We simplify these segments into the dimensions of progressiveness-conservatism (González et al., 2022) and individual influence (Simpson et al., 2015).

In a communal context, individuals often face a binary choice, either supporting or opposing a plan, thereby categorising themselves as supporters or opponents. Decision-making within this community is influenced by experiential needs, social needs, and values. Individuals rely on their direct experiences, adherence to prevailing social norms, and alignment with fundamental beliefs, respectively (Antosz et al., 2019). Conflicts may emerge when agents experience a discrepancy between these needs. For example, individuals may reject a plan based on experiential or value considerations while their social network

³Sinus Milieus. <https://www.sinus-institut.de/en/sinus-milieus/sinus-milieus-germany>

endorses it (social need) can lead to instances of cognitive dissonance. Consequently, individuals take actions to alleviate this cognitive dissonance through various interactions.

In the simulated community, social dynamics are encapsulated in a process where interactions play a crucial role. These interactions involve efforts to persuade others or, conversely, experiences of being influenced by fellow community members. The dynamism of individual opinions and behaviours within this simulated community is significantly enhanced through these interactions with others.

3.1.2 Introductory video of the dialogue tool

To acquaint viewers with the realm of computer simulation and shed light on essential principles of decision-making within a community framework, we have created an informative video for this dialogue tool of INCITE-DEM.

The video highlights diverse results arising from community discussions facilitated by computer simulation. Our primary goal is to encourage individuals to embrace a communal viewpoint when deliberating proposed plans. Access this introductory video through the following link: <https://youtu.be/kGcTSOuLKM8>.

3.2 Design and integration

In essence, the dialogue tool is crafted to extract insights from simulations, shedding light on the complexities of community decision-making while emphasising an understanding of social dynamics and group influence. Its objective is to encourage thoughtful consideration of the balance necessary for strengthening community cohesion and providing strategies to address internal conflicts. Moving beyond mere vote counting, this tool aims to promote the understanding of the forces shaping collective opinions. Importantly, it acts as catalysts for raising awareness about diverse perspectives and potential outcomes, facilitating constructive dialogue among individuals with both similar and opposing views.

For a brief overview of the dialogue tool, you can watch the introductory video (see 3.1.2 <https://youtu.be/kGcTSOuLKM8>). The following sections delve into a more detailed exploration of the dialogue tool.

3.2.1 Key concepts in the dialogue tool

Key components within the dialogue tool for INCITE-DEM encompass the following:

1. *Agents*: Within the simulated community, individuals, or agents, take centre stage in the model, acting as focal points with unique characteristics and behaviours. Agents are categorised using two dimensions: progressiveness-conservatism and the level of influence they have. These individuals are empowered with the right to make decisions, such as binary choices—either supporting or opposing the plan—based on three fundamental needs.

The main characteristics and behaviours of these agents are outlined as follows:

- (1) Group segmentation: Individuals within the community are categorised based on two key dimensions: their level of influence and their stance on progressiveness-conservatism. These dimensions are instrumental in classifying and comprehending the varied perspectives within the simulated community. To enhance accessibility for non-academic audiences, we substitute the terms "vocalisation" for influence and "openness to change" for progressiveness-conservatism.

- (2) **Decision-making process:** The agents engage in a decision-making process where they either adopt or reject the plan. This decision is grounded in how well each option aligns with the agents' three foundational needs: experiential needs (shaped by direct experiences), social needs (influenced by adherence to norms), and value needs (stemming from core beliefs). This comprehensive approach reflects the multi-faceted nature of decision-making within the simulated community.
- (3) **Cognitive dissonance:** Agents might confront conflicts between their experiential, social, and value needs, resulting in cognitive dissonance. To resolve this internal conflict, agents utilise interactional strategies to alleviate dissonance and enhance overall fulfilment. This aspect introduces a dynamic element to the model, capturing the interplay of conflicting needs and the strategies employed by agents to navigate these internal tensions.

2. Interactions: Within their social networks, agents initiate interactions to resolve internal conflicts. These interactions encompass endeavours to persuade or be persuaded by others, encapsulating the social dynamics within the simulated community. These exchanges play a significant role in shaping the evolution of opinions and behaviours.

3. Environment: In the context of the dialogue tool, the term "environment" pertains to the existing social norms within a community, wielding a substantial impact on the outcomes of interactions. Robust norms, for instance, have the effect of rendering individuals more receptive to the opinions of those in their immediate vicinity. This dynamic plays a pivotal role in shaping the overall discourse within the simulated environment, as the prevailing social norms act as an influential backdrop against which discussions unfold and opinions are formed. The environment, in this understanding, becomes a crucial factor in determining the course and dynamics of interactions within the simulated community.

4. Emergence: Within the context of this dialogue tool, the concept of emergence unfolds as a result of collective shifts in opinions or behaviours observed across the entire community. This phenomenon illuminates the cumulative impact generated by individual decisions and interactions over an extended period, emphasising the dynamic nature through which the community undergoes evolution. The emergence phenomenon underscores the interdependence of the constituents within the community, showcasing how the combination of their choices and interactions contributes to the overall trajectory of the community's development.

5. Evolution: Within the dialogue tool of INCITE-DEM unfolds as a dynamic process, wherein individuals' thoughts and actions evolve through their interactions with others. This evolutionary trajectory is marked by several fundamental aspects:

- (1) **Adaptation:** In the simulated setting, individuals display a capacity for adapting. Interacting with peers allows them to absorb new information and diverse viewpoints, potentially leading to shifts in their perspectives and behaviours as they integrate this knowledge into their thinking.
- (2) **Social Influence:** Individuals are part of a connected social network, where the opinions and behaviours of each member are influenced by others. Processes like persuasion and conformity play significant roles, prompting individuals to align with prevailing choices or authoritative figures within the simulated community.
- (3) **Emergence:** As interactions unfold, consensus may arise, and collective norms may develop over time. These emergent dynamics influence the course and outcomes of interactions, shaping the ongoing evolution of opinions and behaviours within the simulated environment.
- (4) **Iteration:** there is a continuous feedback loop in this dialogue tool, where past interactions inform future engagements, guiding individual adaptation. Individuals express their opinions, receive peer feedback, and make iterative adjustments to their thoughts and actions. This iterative process drives the ongoing evolution of opinions and behaviours within the simulated community.

3.2.2 Main mechanism in the dialogue tool

The primary mechanism within the dialogue tool operates as follows (see Figure 2), and the pseudocode for the algorithm governing this process is provided in Appendix 1.

Within the simulated community, individuals form their opinions on whether to support or oppose a plan. Initially, these opinions are shaped by the satisfaction of values and experiential needs, taking into account the overall satisfaction derived from three distinct types of needs:

- (1) Experiential needs: This encompasses the direct experience of the situation, including factors such as costs, noise, smell, and visual aspects.
- (2) Social needs: This involves adherence to the prevailing social norm within the community.
- (3) Values: These are related to the core beliefs held by an agent, such as environmentalism or consumerism.

Figure 2: Process of decision-making of individuals in the dialogue tool

Their initial decision to either adopt or reject a plan is influenced by a thoughtful assessment of which option aligns best with these three foundational needs.

When individuals are in the process of forming their initial opinions regarding certain initiatives, they may struggle with cognitive dissonance and encounter dilemmas, which can be categorised as either social or non-social dilemmas (Antosz et al., 2019).

- (1) A social dilemma arises when a behaviour satisfies experiential needs and values but falls short of meeting social needs or vice-versa. For instance, biking to work satisfies health, speed, and cost-effectiveness (experiential needs) and supports sustainability (values) but may not align with social norms, potentially leading to social dissatisfaction.
- (2) On the other hand, a non-social dilemma encompasses experiential and values dilemmas. The experiential dilemma occurs when a behaviour satisfies social needs and values but not

experiential needs or when experiential needs are met while social needs and values are not. For example, insulating a house may be costly and disruptive (experiential dissatisfaction) but gains approval from renovating neighbours (social satisfaction) and aligns with environmental sustainability (values). The values dilemma arises when a behaviour satisfies experiential and social needs but conflicts with values or when values are met while experiential and social needs are not. Driving to work, for instance, satisfies comfort and popularity (experiential and social needs) but harms the environment (values dissatisfaction).

When individuals in the community face cognitive dissonance resulting from both social and non-social dilemmas, social interactions become common as a means to alleviate this dissonance.

This interaction or communication reflects a motivational state of cognitive dissonance, prompting individuals to either seek information from specific parts of their neighbours (Inquiring strategy) or share information with particular members of the neighbours (signalling strategy).

- (1) The signalling strategy involves individuals attempting to identify someone who would be most receptive to changing their opinion.
- (2) In contrast, the inquiring strategy entails individuals seeking to uphold their cognitions and initiating a search that maximises the likelihood of receiving information aligning with their slightly preferred alternative.

3.3 Development of the dialogue tool

There are currently three primary types of tools for implementing agent-based simulation systems:

- (1) Fundamental programming languages like Python, MatLab, Java, and others;
- (2) Well-structured frameworks exemplified by JADE;
- (3) Platforms based on modelling and simulation, including AnyLogic, NetLogo, and others.

We have chosen NetLogo as the platform for developing the dialogue tool in the INCITE-DEM project. Originating from Uri Wilensky's team in 1990, NetLogo has been consistently developed, maintained, and updated by the Centre for Internet Learning and Computer Modelling at Northwestern University⁴.

NetLogo⁵ is widely acknowledged as a simple yet powerful environment for modelling complexity (Tisue & Wilensky, 2004), making it a robust platform for simulating multi-agent systems across both natural and social phenomena (Wilensky & Rand, 2015). Distinguished by its user-friendly interface, cross-platform compatibility, and specialised capability for analysing complex adaptive systems, NetLogo is the ideal choice for the INCITE-DEM project. It empowers users to navigate the intricacies of individual behaviours at the micro-level while uncovering macro patterns that emerge from complex interactions among entities. By establishing rules and commands directed at individual "agents", NetLogo facilitates a profound exploration of the micro-level, simultaneously revealing the complexities that contribute to macro-level patterns.

Additionally, NetLogo enhances the simulation experience with an extensive array of sophisticated models available in the NetLogo model library⁶.

⁴ Center for Connected Learning and Computer-Based Modeling, Northwestern University. <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo> (1999)

⁵ NetLogo user manual. <https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/docs/>

⁶ NetLogo model library. <https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/models/>

3.4 Installation instructions and basic knowledge of NetLogo

3.4.1 Installation instructions

NetLogo, a freely available open-source software, can be easily installed following these instructions:

1. Download NetLogo:

- (1) Visit the official NetLogo website at <https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/6.4.0/>.
- (2) Go to the "Download" section.
- (3) Select the version compatible with your laptop's operating system, either Windows or macOS.

2. Install NetLogo

- (1) Once the download is complete, execute the downloaded file.
- (2) Follow the on-screen instructions to proceed with the NetLogo installation.
- (3) Opt for the default settings unless you have specific preferences.

3. Launch NetLogo:

- (1) After installation, launch NetLogo either from the applications folder or by searching for it using spotlight.
- (2) Alternatively, create a shortcut for convenient access.

In addition to installing the software, an alternative option is to utilise NetLogo Web. This web-based version enables you to either open pre-built models or create your own, offering a versatile and easily accessible means to interact with the capabilities of NetLogo. The instructions for using NetLogo Web will be demonstrated in the following section.

3.4.2 Basic knowledge of NetLogo

NetLogo is a versatile Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) platform designed to simulate and explore complex systems, both natural and social phenomena. Here are some fundamental concepts to understand about NetLogo:

1. *Agent*. In NetLogo, four distinct types of entities are known as agents: turtles, patches, links, and the observer.

- (1) Turtles are mobile agents capable of movement within the NetLogo environment.
- (2) Patches define the two-dimensional world of NetLogo, forming a grid where each square unit serves as a traversable surface for turtles.
- (3) Links are specialised agents responsible for connecting two turtles. These connections can be either directed, signifying a link from one turtle to another, or undirected, indicating a connection between two turtles.
- (4) The observer is a unique agent in that there is only one instance of it, and it lacks a specific location. In the context of NetLogo, the observer can be conceptualised as the conductor orchestrating the entire simulation.

While some descriptions of agent-based models exclusively label turtles as agents, excluding patches and links, and often omit the observer, it is crucial to recognise that, in NetLogo, all four entities—turtles, patches, links, and the observer—are considered agents according to NetLogo documentation.

Figure 3: Primary window of NetLogo

2. The main interface of NetLogo consists of several components, refer to Figure 3.

(1) Three tabs: the interface tab, the info tab and the code tab

- 1) The *Interface tab* functions as the central control hub for model execution, encompassing diverse components such as buttons, sliders, switches, monitors and plots. Key features include the "RESET" and "SETUP" buttons, which initialise the model, and the "GO" button, which executes the model.
- 2) The *Info tab* facilitates the incorporation of model documentation.
- 3) Within the *Code tab*, you will discover the primary body of the model's code. It's important to mention that, in certain models, a section of the code may be integrated into the plots on the Interface tab.

(2) Control the speed of the model running. To adjust the model execution speed, the default setting is "normal speed". Moving the slider to the right accelerates the model while shifting it to the left decelerates the model.

(3) Ticks. Indicates the duration of the model's runtime. In typical models, the tick counter commences at 0 and increments by 1 in integer increments.

Figure 4: Display of the command centre

(4) The command centre functions as the interface for output messages and enables interaction with the model through commands. As an illustration, consider the "show and count" command. Enter the following into the command centre: "Show count turtles". This will prompt NetLogo to display the count of turtles in the model, as depicted in Figure 4.

(5) Basic controls, such as buttons, sliders, monitors, and graphs, are employed to engage with the model and comprehend its operations. Users customise these controls based on the specific requirements of their application, as not all models necessitate, for instance, a graphical representation of results.

3.4.3 Access to the dialogue tool

There exist four approaches for accessing and employing the dialogue tool. In this section, we exclusively illustrate the method for accessing the tool, while its demonstration and utilisation will be elaborated in Section 4. It is noteworthy that although the main window of the dialogue tool may exhibit variations based on the access method, the fundamental mechanisms, functions, and usage remain consistent.

Method 1: Access the dialogue tool through the web

When maintaining a stable internet connection, you can access the dialogue tool via the INCITE-DEM website: <https://incite-dem.eu/dialogue-tool-2/>.

This represents the most straightforward method, alleviating the need for downloading the software or the dialogue tool independently. The tool is easily accessible through the provided link (<https://shaoni-wang.github.io/incite-dem/dialogue-tool.html>) and can be directly utilised on the webpage, as depicted in Figure 5. Accessing the tool through the web is the preferred option in INCITE-DEM.

Figure 5: Main window of the dialogue tool

Upon scrolling down, the Model Info tab becomes visible. By clicking to unfold the model tab, one can access comprehensive information about the dialogue tool, as illustrated in Figure 6.

STEP 4: Running the model

SETUP-COMMUNITY
GO ONCE GO

Command Center [dropdown arrow]

NetLogo Code [dropdown arrow]

Model Info [dropdown arrow]

WHAT IS IT?

This model aims to replicate the evolution of opinions and behaviours on a communal plan over time. It also aims to foster community dialogue on simulation outcomes, promoting inclusivity and engagement. Individuals (referred to as agents), grouped based on Sinus Milieus (Groh-Samberg et al., 2023), face a binary choice: support or oppose the plan. Motivated by experiential, social, and value needs (Antosz et al., 2019), their decision is influenced by how well the plan aligns with these fundamental needs.

HOW IT WORKS

During the model's operation, agents decide whether to support a plan, designated as the "green hat", or oppose it, denoted as the "red hat". Their choice between supporting or opposing is determined by a calculation that takes into account both their satisfaction with these options and the influence of social norms. Agents' satisfaction can be categorized into three dimensions based on their needs: experiential, social, and value-driven.

- Experiential need refers to your daily experience. Does the plan make your life more comfortable, and does it save money for example?
- Social need refers to your (dis)agreement with others. Do most of the people you know share your position, or are you the outlier in the group, making you an outcast?

Figure 6: Model Info tab of the dialogue tool

Method 2: Access the dialogue tool directly within the NetLogo modelling commons

The NetLogo modelling commons functions as a repository for various models, fostering the sharing and discussion of more than 1,000 agent-based models created by modellers globally. The dialogue tool of INCITE-DEM has been uploaded to the modelling commons and can be conveniently accessed via the following link: http://modelingcommons.org/browse/one_model/7349#model_tabs_browse_info.

Figure 7: "Run in NetLogo Web" tab within the NetLogo modelling commons

To initiate the dialogue tool, simply click on the "Run in NetLogo Web" tab, as depicted in Figure 7.

With this approach, you do not have to download this dialogue tool (needs to be downloaded when using Method 3 in the following part). Furthermore, when scrolling down, you will come across the "Model Info" tab, which functions similarly to Method 1 (depicted in Figure 6).

Method 3: Access the dialogue tool with NetLogo Web

- Step 1: Visit the NetLogo modelling commons first using the link http://modelingcommons.org/browse/one_model/7349#model_tabs_browse_info.
- Step 2: Click to download the file named "Dialogue tool of the INCITE-DEM.nlogo" (refer to Figure 7 in Method 2).
- Step 3: Proceed to NetLogo Web by visiting the link <https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/>. Click on the "Go to NetLogo Web" icon, leading you to a randomly opened model from the NetLogo model library, exemplified by Figure 8 (Segregation Model).

Figure 8: Interface of the segregation model within the NetLogo web

- Step 4: Opt for the "upload a model" option positioned in the top right corner (refer to Figure 8) to upload the previously downloaded file of the "Dialogue tool of the INCITE-DEM.nlogo."
- Step 5: Upon completion of Step 4, a webpage resembling Figure 9 will be displayed.

Scrolling down reveals the Model Info section (similar to Figure 6 in Method 1), containing information on the introduction and utilisation of the dialogue tool.

Figure 9: Window of dialogue tool within NetLogo web

Method 4: Open the dialogue tool with NetLogo software

The aforementioned three methods are contingent on internet connectivity. To employ the dialogue tool in an offline setting, it is recommended to download the model when internet access is accessible. This permits unrestricted usage independent of an internet connection, facilitating the execution of the downloaded model using NetLogo software.

Moreover, for NetLogo modellers and agent-based modellers, it is advised to interact with the model through the NetLogo software. The detailed procedures are elaborated as follows:

- Step 1: Begin by downloading and installing NetLogo on your PC or laptop, as illustrated in Section 3.4.1.
- Step 2: Download the file named “Dialogue tool of the INCITE-DEM.nlogo” (refer to Figure 7) via the link http://modelingcommons.org/browse/one_model/7349#model_tabs_browse_info.
- Step 3: Open the previously downloaded file using NetLogo, and you will be presented with an interface as depicted in Figure 10 (in section 3.5.1).

3.5 Dialogue tool of INCITE-DEM in NetLogo

In this section, we will clarify the features and main contents of the dialogue tool. We will utilise the software version as an illustrative example, acknowledging that minimal variations may exist in other versions.

3.5.1 Main interface

We utilised NetLogo 6.3 programming to craft a model reflecting the intricacies of community dynamics (Wilensky, 1999). The model interface for the dialogue tool of INCITE-DEM,

depicted in Figure 10, encompasses four key components: a command interface, a control interface, an output interface, and the simulated community.

- (1) The *command interface* facilitates the issuance of various commands, including but not limited to system initialisation (RESET and SETUP), the creation of specific agents based on predefined parameters (ADD-AGENTS), the execution of a single step (GO ONCE), and the initiation of continuous execution (GO).
- (2) The *control interface* of the model is designed to enable the adjustment of various parameters, affording the creation of diverse scenarios. Parameter manipulation primarily involves the use of sliders and switches, exemplified during the configuration of the group stage.
 - In the initialisation stage, several crucial parameters are set: "num-agents," determining the population size within the group, and "time-for-voting" for community voting duration.
 - Two additional parameters, namely "against-or-for-change" and "less-or-more-vocal," symbolise "progressiveness" and "influence" (as outlined in section 3.2.1). Values approaching 1 indicate an inclination towards openness to change or vocalisation, while values nearing 0 indicate a preference for the status quo and less vocalisation.
 - Lastly, the boolean parameter "show-label?" functions as an indicator of whether to display the identification number as a label within the group. The "show-links?" switch, when activated, reveals the links between agents, providing visibility into the community structure. Conversely, when the switch is turned off, the links remain concealed.
- (3) The system's *output interface* comprises both model feature output and model operation result output, visually depicted within the box containing group information and operational results plots in the model system. This display communicates crucial information related to the generated groups. For a detailed insight into the system's performance under various parameters, researchers can refer to the simulation results output.
 - The "%Opponents" and "%Supporters" indicate the percentage of agents opposing or supporting a plan within the community, with both values evolving.
 - The visual model also incorporates the counts of supporters for alternative options, along with the count of happy or unhappy individuals when supporting or opposing a plan (or an alternative, innovation).
- (4) The groups and agents in the *simulated community* (simulated world) are designed on two dimensions: "less-or-more-vocal" and "against-or-for-change". In this graphical depiction, the vertical axis measures individual satisfaction, with elevated positions indicating greater contentment. Conversely, the horizontal axis represents the level of support for the plan (innovation), with groups positioned to the right demonstrating stronger backing for the initiative.

In the realm of the simulated world, we employ several methods to categorise and express distinctions among agents. Firstly, we discern various groups based on the colour of the agents. Secondly, we utilise coloured hats as symbolic representations of diverse opinions or behaviours. Lastly, we employ happy and sad facial expressions as indicators to convey the level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction experienced by these individuals (See Section 4.2 for more details).

Figure 10: User interface of the dialogue tool of the INCITE-DEM

3.5.2 Operation of the tool

During the operation of the tool, agents in the simulated community make decisions regarding their stance on a plan, represented by the "green hat" for support or the "red hat" for opposition. This choice is influenced by a calculation considering their satisfaction with available options, as detailed in section 3.2.2. Agents' satisfaction is classified into three dimensions based on their needs:

- (1) Experiential needs: This pertains to daily experiences, assessing whether the plan enhances comfort or saves money, for instance.
- (2) Social needs: This reflects alignment or disagreement with others. Agents consider whether their position aligns with the majority, making them part of the consensus, or if they diverge, potentially leading to social isolation.
- (3) Value-driven needs: This involves important personal beliefs, such as environmental concerns or economic welfare considerations.

Individual opinions, stemming from diverse groups, may vary, and these opinions evolve dynamically through interactions with connected peers until the final vote on the plan. Interactions provide individuals with opportunities to persuade or be persuaded by others, leading to shifts in favour or against the plan.

3.5.3 Simulation result output

The output of the system visually represents its performance across a range of parameters, providing researchers and model users with a thorough comprehension of the results.

- (1) The "%OPPONENTS" reveals the percentage of individuals opposing a plan, while "%SUPPORTERS" indicates supporting individuals, both evolving.

- (2) The "SUPPORTER-or-OPPONENT?" graph depicts the temporal evolution of individual preferences between supporters (green hat) and opponents (red hat) within a specified timeframe.
- (3) The "HAPPY(+), NEUTRAL(), or UNHAPPY(-)?" chart evaluates the happiness of individuals based on their decisions to oppose or support the plan. Labels such as "opponent+" indicate satisfied opposing individuals (depicted as a smiling face with a red hat), "opponent-" signifies dissatisfied opposers (a sad face with a red hat), and "opponent" represents neutral opposition (a neutral face with a red hat). Similarly, the terms "supporters+", "supporters-", and "supporters" denote satisfaction, dissatisfaction, or neutrality among supporting individuals (with green hat).

3.6 Summary

This chapter begins by introducing a tool that helps diverse groups of people understand each other better, promoting inclusivity in democratic innovations. It starts by explaining the tool's main purpose and introducing key concepts that are essential for its operation.

The chapter then moves on to the development phase, focusing on the deliberate choice of using NetLogo as the platform for creating this dialogue tool. It provides basic knowledge of NetLogo to help readers understand the development environment. The chapter also explains how to access the dialogue tool, ensuring that it is user-friendly for a wide audience.

The chapter also guides readers through the purpose-driven features and core mechanisms of the dialogue tool, emphasising NetLogo's role in facilitating meaningful discussions among stakeholders with diverse perspectives.

By the end of the chapter, readers not only understand the purpose and functionality of the dialogue tool but also receive practical instructions on how to access it.

4 Utilisation of the dialogue tool

In this section, we utilise the software version as an illustrative example to highlight the setup and utilisation of the dialogue tool. As mentioned in section 3.5, it is essential to underscore that while there may be slight variations in other versions, the fundamental procedure remains consistent.

4.1 Guidelines for utilisation

To deploy this dialogue tool, follow a four-step sequence. The initial three steps constitute the setup phase, where the model is readied for execution. Start by resetting the model, then proceed to configure the community and set up groups. The final step involves executing the model.

For further guidance, we've created a tutorial video illustrating the utilisation of the dialogue tool (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r_ri0Ax5MU&ab_channel=INCITE-DEM), showcasing three specific scenarios: happy supporters, a divided community, and unhappy supporters. Additional details, implementation clarifications, as well as associated commands and parameters, are provided in the subsequent steps.

Step 1: Reset the model

Click the "RESET" button (see Figure 11) to erase all elements within the model's environment thoroughly.

STEP 1: Reset the model

Figure 11: Reset button in the dialogue tool at Step 1

Step 2: Setting the community

In this step, create the community by defining its characteristics as illustrated in Figure 12. This involves primarily utilising two sliders to adjust two parameters.

STEP 2: Setting the community

Figure 12: Sliders in the dialogue tool at Step 2

- (1) The "num-groups" slider adjusts the number of distinct groups within the simulated community, ranging up to a maximum value of 10. In this instance, it is set to 2.
- (2) The "time-voting" slider sets the duration for voting, specifying the timeframe for model execution, with a maximum value of 200. Here, it is set to 80.

Step 3: Setting the group

While defining groups with diverse properties is feasible, it's important to acknowledge that agents within these groups may vary. To account for this diversity in the model, agents within groups are generated based on two characteristics: "against-or-for-change" and "less-or-more-vocal." These

characteristics are visually represented by indicating the group property, while the population of the specific group is denoted by "num-agents" (refer to Figure 13).

The process of creating groups in the simulated community involves the following steps:

- (1) Identify the desired group characteristics during this step by adjusting the two sliders, namely "against-or-for-change" and "less-or-more-vocal." Determine the size of the group by adjusting the slider labelled "num-agents".
- (2) Click the "ADD-AGENTS" button to create the group in the simulated world.
- (3) To create additional groups, repeat the above two procedures as needed.

STEP 3: Setting the group

Figure 13: Sliders and buttons in the dialogue tool at Step 3

Combining the features of "against-or-for-change", "less-or-more-vocal", and "num-agents" enables the creation of distinct groups, such as a small and vocal faction in favour of a plan or a larger "silent majority" opposed to it. The functionality of these sliders and the "ADD-AGENTS" button is detailed below:

- (1) "against-or-for-change" slider: Governs an agent's inclination to maintain or alter their behaviour, reflecting their openness to change. Values near 1 indicate an openness to change, while values near 0 signify a preference for the status quo.
- (2) "less-or-more-vocal" slider: Measures the audibility of an individual's voice, where higher values signify increased influence. A value approaching 1 indicates a more influential voice, whereas a value close to 0 suggests diminished vocal impact. If individuals are more vocal, the size of their representation as agents would be larger.
- (3) "num-agents" slider: Allows specification of the number of agents within a given group.
- (4) "ADD-AGENTS" button: Executes the command to create a group of agents based on the selected parameters for "against-or-for-change", "less-or-more-vocal", and "num-agents".

Step 4: Running the model

To prepare the model for execution, first, configure the community by clicking the "SETUP-COMMUNITY" button (Figure 14), which allows for the comprehensive setup of the entire system. Subsequently, choose between the "GO ONCE" or "GO" options:

- (1) "GO ONCE": Initiates the model to execute for a single time step.
- (2) "GO" function: Activates continuous execution of the model, facilitating the generation of progress and outcomes based on the specified configurations.

STEP 4: Running the model

Figure 14: Command buttons in the dialogue tool at Step 4

4.2 Symbolic representation

In this conceptual framework, the arrangement of visual components adheres to a specified symbolic arrangement:

1. Representation of individuals and communities:

Individual agents are symbolically depicted as nodes or heads (as illustrated in Figure 15 (1)). These individuals are then grouped, forming connections (represented as links) among themselves. Within the simulation, they engage in communication and influence one another, akin to a community of neighbours exchanging ideas and opinions, as depicted in Figure 15 (2).

2. Group categorisation:

Within a given community, individuals can be categorised into various groups. Each distinct group is distinguished by the colour of its members' faces. For instance, in Figure 15(2), there are Group Pink (with pink-faced individuals) and Group Blue (with blue-faced individuals).

3. Representation of connections:

The connections between these individuals are visually depicted using connecting lines or edges. "Dashed lines" indicate connections between different groups, while "solid lines" signify connections within the same group.

Figure 15: Representation of a single person and a community in the dialogue tool

4. Individual opinions and emotional responses

Individuals exhibit distinct opinions and emotional reactions, which are visually represented in various ways. The specific opinions of individuals are indicated by the colour of their hats, classified as either "green" or "red," with "red" indicating opposition and "green" signifying support. Additionally, their emotional states are conveyed through facial expressions, encompassing happiness, sadness, or neutrality, reflecting their levels of satisfaction, dissatisfaction, or indifference.

For instance, in Figure 16 (1), a smiling face adorned with a green hat signifies a happy supporter. Furthermore, the presence of a blue-faced individual suggests alignment with the blue group, potentially embracing pro-innovation sentiments. The green hat further denotes support for the discussed plan, while the broad smile indicates satisfaction with the proposal.

Conversely, in Figure 16 (2), a sad expression coupled with a red hat denotes an unhappy opponent. The presence of a pink-faced individual implies an association with the pink group, potentially favouring the

status quo. Furthermore, the red hat signifies opposition to the plan, while the sad expression reflects dissatisfaction with the current scenario.

Moreover, individuals may also exhibit indifference, lacking expressions of happiness or sadness towards the plan, as depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 16: Representation of a happy supporter and an unhappy opponent

5. Individual influence dynamics

In community discussions, the active involvement of participants and the inclusion of diverse perspectives play pivotal roles in enriching the discourse and fostering inclusivity. This dynamic interaction can be faithfully reproduced within our simulation through intergroup communication. For example, consider the interaction between the blue group, known for its inclination towards innovation, and the pink group, which tends to prefer maintaining the status quo.

It's crucial to recognise that certain groups may demonstrate more pronounced tendencies for vocalisation than others. To simulate this characteristic, we can adjust the sizes of the agents, resembling heads, within our simulation. The extent of an agent's verbal engagement is directly proportional to the size of its representation.

As illustrated in Figure 17 (1), larger individuals typically exhibit a greater propensity for being outspoken and assertive, readily expressing their viewpoints. In contrast, smaller individuals, as depicted in Figure 17 (2), tend to adopt a more reserved stance, opting for limited engagement. This difference in size reflects variations in assertiveness and the inclination for verbal expression within the simulated community.

Figure 17: Representation of an indifferent outspoken supporter and an indifferent silent opponent

4.3 Things to notice

Maintaining the smooth operation of the dialogue tool necessitates readiness for unexpected occurrences. Here are the critical aspects to consider:

- (1) Reset button: This feature offers a reliable method for restoring order and ensuring procedural accuracy when needed.

- (2) Population size increase: A noticeable uptick in connections may occur, potentially impeding model efficiency and leading to system failures.
- (3) Conservative population sizing: Implementing cautious population sizing helps alleviate risks linked to increased connections, thereby improving model responsiveness and resilience against breakdowns.
- (4) Static parameters: It's crucial to maintain static parameters during model execution to prevent interference with other variables.
- (5) Connections between individuals: As the model advances, connections between individuals become more apparent, indicating heightened interaction frequency. Weakened connections signal reduced interaction, while vanished connections imply no communication.

These points underscore the importance of maintaining stability, managing population size, and understanding connection dynamics within the dialogue tool.

4.4 Summary

This chapter serves as a practical guide to using the dialogue tool, focusing on its setup and operational procedures. Readers are led through a systematic walkthrough, acquainting them with the sequential steps necessary to configure and employ the tool effectively. Visual graphics are incorporated to depict various representations within the simulated community, enhancing understanding.

Moreover, the chapter highlights essential considerations for users to ensure optimal outcomes and minimize errors while utilising the tool. By exploring its features, readers gain insight into its functionalities and capabilities, offering a thorough overview of its utility.

In summary, this chapter delivers a concise yet comprehensive overview of the dialogue tool, empowering readers with the knowledge needed to navigate its complexities.

5 Investigation of the demonstration experiments through the dialogue tool

Picture a case in which a local government suggests building a road through a residential area. In such a case, every member of the community possesses the privilege to cast their vote in support of or opposition to the proposal. The choices made by residents are multifaceted, shaped by factors like convenience, safety, aesthetics, and ecological concerns, leading to a myriad of initially diverse opinions.

As the proposal advances, residents actively engage in interactions, fostering a continuous exchange of ideas and opinions over time. This ongoing interaction serves as a platform for the evolution of perspectives, potentially leading to shifts in individuals' viewpoints. Consequently, the final choices made by residents when they cast their votes may differ from their initial inclinations.

Our experiments aim to simulate the potential dynamics and outcomes in different situations, each one involving a different community, characterised by unique attributes. This includes representation from both proponents and opponents of the proposed road, as well as communities with differing levels of vocal expression.

5.1 Happy supporters

5.1.1 Experiment design

Objective: The goal is to simulate the dynamics and outcomes arising from a community's decision-making process regarding the construction of a road within the community.

For the community representation, let's consider that there are two divergent groups within this community:

- (1) Every resident possesses the right to participate in the decision-making process.
- (2) The community comprises a total of 40 residents, divided into two distinct groups: Group 1 (pink face) and Group 2 (blue face), each consisting of 20 individuals (see Figure 18). Both groups express support for the proposed change, differing in their vocal expression levels, as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameter settings for the community of happy supporters experiment

Group	Group 1	Group 2
Num-agents	20	20
Less-or-more vocal	G1=0.4	G2=0.6
Against-or-for change	G1=0.8	G2=0.8

The simulation extends over 80 rounds, symbolising the progression of the voting process over time. Throughout the voting process, residents are encouraged to engage in discussions, striving to persuade others to align with their viewpoints. Group 2 adopts more vocal and persuasive techniques, contrasting with the quieter yet equally supportive approach employed by Group 1.

5.1.2 Result and analysis

Initialised the model as previously demonstrated, we obtain the evolution pattern of this community in this particular scenario, as displayed in Figure 18.

Figure 18 (1) presents a visual representation of the community structure featuring two distinct representative groups, identifiable through facial colouration. Initially, a spectrum of opinions prevails among community members regarding the proposed idea, delineated within specific parameters. The predominant sentiment aligns with favourability, situated on the right side of the graph, where smiling faces adorned with green hats signify happy supporters. In contrast, a smaller subset expresses discontent with sad faces while still supporting the proposal. Conversely, a minority positioned on the left side of the graph opposes the proposal, featuring red-hatted faces reflecting varying degrees of satisfaction (smiling faces) or dissatisfaction (sad faces) within their opposition.

As time progresses, community discussions evolve, sparking a dynamic transformation in collective perspectives on the proposal. Even those with initially uncertain views demonstrate a propensity to fluctuate between supporting and opposing positions.

Figure 18 (2) illustrates the evolution of some initial supporters (as indicated in Figure 18 (1)) transforming into opponents following interactions, paralleled by a concurrent shift where initial opponents become supporters. Notably, a growing number of individuals who initially opposed the proposal shifted their stance to become supporters over time, reaching a point of unanimous endorsement by the time of the vote at tick 80 (see Figure 18 (3)). This convergence marks the establishment of a unified community marked by satisfied support, identified as a community of happy supporters. This represents the optimal outcome, indicating universal satisfaction and approval within the community regarding the road construction plan.

Figure 18: Evolution of the community of happy supporters at tick 0, 30, and 80

Apart from observing the visual representation of the evolving pattern of collective opinions under the given settings, a more direct insight into the results is evident in Figure 19. This figure illustrates the counts of opponents and supporters throughout the entire duration between the initiation and the voting period. The data indicates a reciprocal influence between both groups, ultimately resulting in a unanimous vote in favour of the road development initiative. The interplay between supporters and

opponents highlights a dynamic process where perspectives evolve, ultimately converging towards a collective decision to endorse the road development proposal.

Figure 19: Fluctuations of supporters and opponents in the happy supporter community over time

Furthermore, upon closer examination of Figure 20, we can observe the fluctuations in the emotional states of both supporters and opponents within the simulated community. The "opponents+" curve reflects the count of opponents with smiling faces, indicating their contentment with their choice. Conversely, "opponents-" represent unsatisfied or unhappy opponents, while "opponents" account for the neutral faces in the simulated community—individuals voting against the plan without expressing happiness or unhappiness. Likewise, the curves representing supporters categorize individuals as either satisfied ("supporters+"), unsatisfied ("supporters-"), or neutral ("supporters"), in their endorsement of the plan.

Figure 20: Fluctuations in the emotional states of supporters and opponents within the community of happy supporters

Notably, the curve for happy supporters ("supporters+") continues to steadily rise as all individuals transition into supporters after tick 50. Concurrently, the curve for unhappy supporters ("supporters-")

experiences a decline. This phenomenon can be attributed to the social psychological concept emphasised by Ertug et al. (2022): individuals tend to experience greater satisfaction when surrounded by like-minded individuals.

5.2 A divided community

5.2.1 Experiment design

Objective: This study builds upon the framework of Experiment 5.1, also aiming to simulate the dynamic and outcomes resulting from a community's decision-making process regarding the implementation of a road within the community, but focusing on a different community with unique characteristics.

For the community representation, we assume a stratification into two distinct groups (refer to Figure 19), each exhibiting unique behavioural characteristics in the context of the road implementation decision-making process.

- (1) Opponents of change (Group 1, pink face): This group opposes the implementation of the road and exhibits a comparatively lower level of verbal expression.
- (2) Advocates for change (Group 2, blue face): This group actively supports and promotes the implementation of the road. Members are characterised by a high level of vocal expression.

Please refer to Table 2 for the detailed parameter settings that will govern the simulation. These settings will define key aspects of the experiment, shaping the interactions and decision-making processes within the simulated community.

Table 2: Parameter settings for the divided community experiment

Group	Group 1	Group 2
Num-agents	20	20
Less-or-more vocal	G1=0.4	G2=0.6
Against-or-for change	G1=0.2	G2=0.8

The simulation is designed to span 80 rounds. Its objective is to investigate potential outcomes within the community decision-making process specific to this scenario. The analysis will focus on discerning the dynamics between vocal advocates for change and less expressive opponents, aiming to comprehend their collective impact on the ultimate decision outcomes.

5.2.2 Results and analysis

In accordance with the experimental design, we firstly observe the evolution of the opinion structure within the community. Figure 21(1) depicts the initial state, where the majority in Group 1 (pink faces) opts to oppose the plan, while the majority in Group 2 (blue faces) chooses to support it.

As the interaction progresses, individuals within and across the groups begin exchanging their opinions. Following a period of discussion on the proposal, a notable opposition (see Figure 21(2)) emerges between these two representative groups. The connection between the different groups weakens, a

consequence of deteriorating interactions between them. Ultimately, at the conclusion of the observed period (refer to Figure 21(3)), the two groups within the community undergo complete isolation from each other, assuming opposing stances.

Due to this outcome, we characterise this situation as a divided community, which is an undesirable scenario that we aim to prevent.

Figure 21: Evolution of a divided community at tick 0, 40, and 80

The dynamics of supporters and opponents in the simulation are illustrated in Figure 22. Upon observation, it becomes evident that, following a period of fluctuation, the community stabilises, attaining a state where the number of supporters equals the number of opponents.

Figure 22: Fluctuations of supporters and opponents in the divided community over time

The interpretation of the curves in Figure 23 aligns with the explanations of Figure 20, provided in Section 5.1.2. Despite an equal total number of supporters and opponents, as indicated in Figure 22, there is a notable disparity in the count of happy opponents compared to happy supporters.

This phenomenon implies that individuals within the subgroup opposing the plan may cast their vote against it while feeling dissatisfied with their choice. It underscores the influence of group norms (Chung

& Rimal, 2016), as individuals may prioritise conformity over making a decision aligned with their personal satisfaction regarding the proposal.

Figure 23: Fluctuations in the emotional states of supporters and opponents within the divided community

5.3 Unhappy supporters

5.3.1 Experiment design

Objective: The principal objective of this experiment closely aligns with the objectives of the preceding 2 studies, delving into the dynamics of a distinct community setting. The aim is to uncover the implications of the community decision-making process within this unique context.

In framing the community representation, let's take into account the presence of two distinct groups within this community as well.

- (1) Group 1 (Pink Face): Comprising individuals less vocal and resistant to change.
- (2) Group 2 (Pink Face): Encompassing individuals highly supportive of change and characterised by heightened vocal expression.

Table 3: Parameter settings for the community of unhappy supporters experiment

Group	Group 1	Group 2
Num-agents	20	20
Less-or-more vocal	G1=0.4	G2=0.6
Against-or-for change	G1=0.4	G2=0.8

Refer to Table 3 for the detailed parameter settings governing this experiment. The central inquiry revolves around the potential consequences emerging from the interaction between these two contrasting groups within the community. The exploration seeks to understand how the interplay

between the less vocal opposition and the vocally expressive advocates for change shapes the outcomes of the decision-making process.

5.3.2 Results and analysis

In accordance with the experimental design, we examine the evolving opinion structure within the community. Initially, as illustrated in Figure 24 (1), individuals in two groups display a varied spectrum of opinions on the proposal. Irrespective of being opponents or supporters, a majority convey satisfaction with their choices, as evidenced by the prevalence of smiling faces.

Figure 24: Evolution of the community of unhappy supporters at tick 0, 40, and 80

Subsequent to a period of discussion, a noteworthy transformation unfolds as some individuals transition from being opponents to supporters. By the conclusion of the voting period, depicted in Figure 24 (3), all individuals align as supporters, albeit with sad faces, signalling their dissatisfaction with the collective decision. In this scenario, many individuals vote in favour of the proposal while expressing dissatisfaction. Hence, we call it an unhappy community.

Figure 25: Fluctuations of supporters and opponents in the community of unhappy supporters over time

Examining Figure 25, it becomes apparent that at the initiation of the proposal, there is an equal number of supporters and opponents. Following a period of fluctuation, the balance shifts, and supporters come to dominate the community. Beyond the overall counts, Figure 26 provides a detailed view of the fluctuation in the number of individuals expressing happiness or unhappiness among both opponents and supporters.

Figure 26: Fluctuations in the emotional states of supporters and opponents within the community of unhappy supporters

Notably, Figure 26 reveals a significant decrease in the count of happy opponents, represented by the curve labelled "opponents+". Concurrently, there is a substantial increase in the number of unhappy supporters, as evidenced by the rise in the curve labelled "supporters-".

This phenomenon can be explained by opponents being influenced to change their position and align with the supporters due to social pressure. Despite their alignment with the majority, the internal conflict causes them to feel unhappy about their decision.

5.4 Discussion

The conducted simulation experiments have proven to be a valuable tool for gaining insights into the complexity of community decision-making processes, especially when faced with critical decisions. The primary objective of these experiments was to capture the dynamic interplay of opinions, the influence of social dynamics, and the range of potential outcomes that communities might experience during such crucial moments.

One of the key takeaways from these simulations is the acknowledgement of the multifaceted nature of community decision-making. The experiments highlight the significance of understanding social dynamics and recognising the considerable impact of group influences. Additionally, the potential for divergent outcomes within a community underscores the complexity inherent in decision-making processes.

These simulations prompt a reflective consideration of the delicate balance required to foster community cohesion. The challenges posed by internal conflicts and differing perspectives come to the forefront, emphasising the need for strategies that navigate these complexities effectively. It becomes evident that successful community decision-making involves more than just counting votes; it requires a deep understanding of the underlying dynamics shaping collective opinions.

Importantly, the simulations serve as a catalyst for raising awareness among individuals about the existence of diverse opinions and the potential outcomes resulting from collective decisions. For instance, the occurrences of divided communities and communities of unhappy supporters spark curiosity, prompting meaningful conversations surrounding the when and why of such phenomena. This, in turn, enhances understanding of the social dynamics at play and encourages constructive dialogue among individuals with both consistent and opposing opinions.

While the simulation does not aim to precisely replicate real-world voting outcomes, its value lies in fostering awareness and facilitating meaningful conversations. By promoting a deeper understanding of the social dynamics involved, individuals are better equipped to navigate and contribute to the decision-making process within their communities. The insights gained from these simulations can inform strategies for addressing undesired phenomena and working towards fostering more informed and satisfied communities in both simulation settings and real-world applications. Moving forward, future simulations and real-world decision-making processes can leverage these insights to construct more efficacious strategies and interventions.

6 Concluding remarks

To promote inclusivity in the realm of democratic innovation, the development of a dialogue tool capable of bridging individuals from diverse groups with varying interests holds significant importance.

Our primary objective centres around creating a dialogue tool for the INCITE-DEM project, employing computer simulation through an agent-based approach. We initiate this process by introducing the agent-based modelling method and the theoretical framework of HUMAT, to simulate individual decision-making processes within the community. In our pursuit of inclusive democratic innovation, we draw insights from the Sinus Milieus to categorise groups, deliberately involving individuals from diverse backgrounds, including those who are disadvantaged.

Subsequently, we proceed to integrate HUMAT, crafting and implementing the dialogue tool using the NetLogo platform. This holistic approach ensures that the tool not only replicates opinions and behaviours but also addresses the unique perspectives of a diverse population, thereby fostering inclusivity in the democratic decision-making process.

Following the demonstration of the core process and mechanisms of individual decision-making within the community, we conduct three demonstration experiments with this dialogue tool, showcasing the tool's efficacy in generating scenarios of a community of happy supporters, a divided community, and a community with unhappy supporters.

The outcomes and engagement with stakeholders (see Appendix 2), including project leaders from Het Hogeland, Ten Boer, and the municipality of Schiermonnikoog, underscore the potential value of the dialogue tool. It exhibits promise in facilitating meaningful discussions and promoting mutual understanding among diverse groups, ultimately contributing to positive transformations within the community and the cultivation of a cohesive and satisfying communal environment.

We acknowledge the significance of ongoing collaboration with a variety of stakeholders in addressing local challenges. Moving forward, our dedication entails enhancing and streamlining the dialogue tool through feedback from stakeholders and insights gained from practical applications.

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Appendix 1 Algorithms of the core processes

The following pseudocode outlines a structured algorithm that guides individuals within a simulated community through the stages of opinion formation, dilemma resolution, and participation in social interactions aimed at mitigating cognitive dissonance.

Initialisation

Define community

Define individuals within the community

Define experiential, social, and value-driven needs

Opinion Formation

For each individual in the community:

 Formulate initial opinions based on experiential, social, and value-driven needs

 # Social Dilemma Evaluation

 If behaviour satisfies experiential needs and values but falls short of meeting social needs, or vice versa:

 Identify and label as a social dilemma

 # Non-Social Dilemma Evaluation

 If experiential dilemma:

 Identify and label as an experiential dilemma

 If values dilemma:

 Identify and label as a value dilemma

Cognitive Dissonance Handling

For each individual in the community facing cognitive dissonance:

 If social dilemma:

 Implement social interaction strategies

Interaction Strategies

For each individual with cognitive dissonance:

 If Inquiring Strategy:

 Seek information from specific parts of their neighbours

 If Signalling Strategy:

 Share information with particular members of the neighbours

Outcome Adjustment

For each individual:

 Adjust opinions based on information obtained through interaction strategies

Iteration

Repeat the process as individuals continue to shape opinions based on evolving circumstances, interactions, and needs satisfaction

Individual interactions

Signalling process

Inquiring process

Appendix 2 Engaging stakeholders in the field

Building connections with community stakeholders is a vital component of our project. Through direct engagement, we seek to establish meaningful relationships and collaboratively address community needs.

1. Het Hogeland

Our first encounter with stakeholders from Het Hogeland on September 11th marked the beginning of our direct engagement with community representatives. This initial meeting provided us with valuable insights into local perspectives and concerns. It became clear that the explanation of what an agent-based model is, and what social simulations imply, requires a lot of attention. Hence we realised the importance of producing a video that people can watch to see and understand how models work and what results they produce. This also implies that the explanatory video is an integral part of the dialogue tool. It can be used as a stand-alone element in making people aware of community dynamics and catalyse a discussion on the perspectives of people having different opinions and people who speak out less. Next, the video serves as a preparation for active working with the simulation tool in a group session. Here the moderator has to be familiarised with the simulation tool before the session.

During the second meeting with Het Hogeland on December 4, 2023, we conducted the test of the introductory video and simulation tool for the first time. Following an introduction and presentation of the video and simulation, participants recognised the video's potential for highlighting community dynamics and raising awareness of the quieter members' interests during community meetings.

Although the simulation tool is designed to be self-explanatory, we explained its added value for communities discussing special conditions, such as more than two groups or a small group with an exceptional position. Participants, with varying computational skills, engaged in recreating community cases and discussed the results. While some faced challenges accessing the simulation tool in the browser, online participants successfully utilised it.

Observing that all participants, regardless of their prior experience with such models, could work with the simulation tool, we concluded that (1) a clear manual for using the tool in a community setting should be provided in advance, and (2) efforts should be made to simplify and make the setup fool-proof. We plan to address these aspects before testing the simulation tool in a real community.

2. Municipality of Schiermonnikoog

On October 6th, we met with individuals employed by the municipality of Schiermonnikoog, including the elderman. Our agenda began with the introduction of the dialogue tool, accompanied by an explanation of the fundamental concepts underlying its mechanism. Subsequently, members of the municipality elucidated the challenges confronting Nieuw Dokkum and outlined the proposed plan for improving the heating system within the Schiermonnikoog community. The primary objective of our collaborative session was to discern the most effective way to integrate the dialogue tool into the real case, ensuring its practicality, relevance, and overall benefits. Also here we learned how important it is to make clear in a simple manner how the agent-based simulations work and what can be learned from them in group sessions. The bottom line is that not the model is the focal point, but catalysing a dialogue between people. Hence it is better to have an overly simple model that is actually being used, than a more

developed model that people do not like to use. Especially as academics from the modelling community, it is important to keep this end goal of usability in mind.

3. Ten Boer

On October 13th, our interaction with Ten Boer project leaders focused on introducing computational simulation in social dynamics. Within this session, we presented the social-influence model, offering project leaders an in-depth grasp of its potential impact. Additionally, we revealed the preliminary version of the dialogue tool, allowing participants to envision its practical application in tackling challenges within the community.

4. Subsequent actions in stakeholder engagement

To further enhance our project's efficacy and responsiveness to community needs, we will undertake the following key initiatives:

- (1) Conduct follow-up meetings: Schedule additional meetings with stakeholders to specifically address their concerns and gather further feedback.
- (2) Iterative refinement of dialogue tool: Continuously refine the dialogue tool based on the valuable insights acquired during engagement sessions. This adaptive approach ensures that the tool remains aligned with the evolving dynamics and requirements of the communities we are working with.
- (3) Establish robust communication channels: Transparent and efficient communication is essential for the success of our project and the sustained involvement of community members.
- (4) Explore contextual integration opportunities: Actively explore opportunities for further integration of the dialogue tool within the unique context of each community. Tailoring the tool to specific needs ensures its relevance and effectiveness in addressing local challenges and aspirations.

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